

Special Relativity From Nonrelativistic Lagrangian Formalism?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Dec. 28, 2021

The Lagrangian formalism was originally introduced as a method of deriving Newton's equations in the nonrelativistic case. Two equations associated with this formalism are: $dL/dv = p$ and $H=pv-L$ where H is the Hamiltonian (often energy) and L the Lagrangian, p momentum and v velocity. If one treats H as E (energy), but insists that p be energy flow i.e. Ev i.e. generalizing $m_0 v$, then one may obtain special relativity.

Nonrelativistic Lagrangian Formalism For a Free Particle

In nonrelativistic formalism, $L = .5mv^2$ for a free particle. Thus, $dL/dv = mv = p = \text{momentum}$. If one considers mass to be a kind of energy that is modified to first order by $.5mv^2$ in the nonrelativistic case, then $p=Ev$ should be the full momentum, if momentum represents energy flow. One may consider rest mass to be like energy because an object at rest is given extra energy i.e. $.5mv^2$ to first order if one applies a force over a distance. If a stationary box contains objects moving back and forth, these are like rest mass as work is needed to accelerate or slow them down as the whole box is accelerated or slowed down. When the box is at rest, the bouncing interior particles, however, are like energy, so rest mass should be like energy too. For the nonrelativistic case: $H=pv - L$ where H is the Hamiltonian and is often the energy. In the nonrelativistic case $H = .5mv^2$, but for a new generalized case, it should be E , the new combined rest mass with movement energy.

Special Relativity

Given $p=dL/dv$ and $H=E=pv-L$ together with the assumption $p=Ev$ one obtains:

$E = v dL/dv - L$ with $1/v (dL/dv) = E$ or:

$$1/v (dL/dv) = v dL/dv - L \quad ((1))$$

This differential equation may be solved to yield:

$$L = - m_0 \sqrt{1-vv} \quad (c=1) \text{ which gives: } p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1-vv} \quad ((2))$$

$$\text{Given that one assumed that } p=Ev, \quad E = m_0 v / \sqrt{1-vv} \quad ((3))$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue that special relativity follows from the nonrelativistic Lagrangian equations: $p=dL/dv$ and $H=E = vp - L$ together with the assumption that $p=Ev$ in a generalized case with E being an unknown function of m_0 and v such that its first correction is $.5m_0 v^2$.

Solving for L one obtains a differential equation with the solution $L = -m_0 \sqrt{1-v^2}$ ($c=1$) from which $p = mv / \sqrt{1-v^2}$. Given the assumption $p=Ev$, $E = m_0 / \sqrt{1-v^2}$. One may show that nonrelativistic mechanics follows from this as a limiting case. Thus nonrelativistic Lagrangian formalism together with the idea $p=Ev$ ie. energy flow where $E(m_0, v)$ yields the relativistic formalism.